

FEATURES OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR MEASURING TEMPERATURE VIA WIRELESS TOUCH NETWORKS

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Abstract. Modern technology allows you to remotely measure and monitor the temperature of a particular object or place. This article presents the capabilities and applications of the DS18B20 temperature sensor and the NodeMCU platform for remote control of the Internet signal transmission system developed by DALLAS Semiconductor.

Keywords: temperature sensor, Wi-Fi, monitoring, wireless network, power supply, NodeMCU system.

Аннотация. Современные технологии позволяют дистанционно измерять и контролировать температуру того или иного объекта или места. В данной статье представлены возможности и области применения датчика температуры DS18B20 и платформы NodeMCU для удаленного управления системой передачи интернет сигналов, разработанной компанией DALLAS Semiconductor.

Ключевые слова: датчик температуры, Wi-Fi, мониторинг, беспроводная сеть, источник питания, система NodeMCU.

Today, there are temperature sensors and systems that work with them. The use of modern wireless technologies and devices for remote monitoring or constant temperature control in systems where regular monitoring of the temperature of facilities, greenhouses or warehouses in industrial zones is important [1]. In particular, it is advisable to control the measurement errors, real-time data transmission, power supply of system elements [2]. The DS18B20 temperature sensor is a single-wire digital temperature sensor. It can be powered by an external power supply or powered from a data line in "interference mode", which eliminates the need for an external power supply [3].

Figure 1. DS18B20 temperature sensor.

Can be set depending on the height and limits of the variable signal. The network support list associated with it (multi-address) is multicast. Thus, multiple DS18B20 can only be parallel in three lines to perform multi-point temperature measurement. Its connection is shown in Figure 2 site [4].

Figure 2. DS18B20 wiring diagram

The DS18B20 smart temperature sensor has several key features. It has a unique single-wire interface. All you need to do to connect the microprocessors and make a two-way connection is to install the command codes. It is not necessary to use any peripheral device [5]. DS18B20 temperature sensor waterproof type is also available. The power supply may be available via a data transmission line and has an appropriate voltage range. The technical characteristics of the DS18B20 temperature sensor are given in Table 1 [6].

Table 1.

Specifications of DS18B20 temperature sensor.

Power supply	3,0 ~ 5,5 VDC
Data transfer	9 ~ 12 bit
Temperature range	-50 °C - +125 °C
Temperature measurement accuracy	+/- 0,5 °C (-10 °C to 85° C)

Sensor size	Diameter: 6 - 9mm, length: 10mm - 1000mm
Device material	Stainless steel
Connection types	Molex, JST, DuPont, CWB, CJT, U type and others.
Heat shrinkable material	PVC pipe; fiberglass tube; teflon pipe
Ports	Black: GND; Yellow: DATA; Red: VDD +

There are currently several systems available for wireless data transmission and real-time monitoring to the user, monitoring the temperature above or below the set norm, or temperature warning. Of the available boards, the common Arduino board or several types of microcontrollers also have very high capacity [7]. GSM, ZigBee, Wi-Fi and other modules can be used with these boards for wireless data transmission. When controlling or monitoring the temperature of objects using temperature sensors, the characteristics of the objects are analyzed by selecting the NodeMCU board [8]. The small size, flexibility of this board, one of the best features of the system is that the Wi-Fi transmission module is located on the board and transmits data from multiple sensors to the user at the same time [9]. NodeMCU is a platform based on the ESP8266 module. NodeMCU (Node Micro Controller Unit) is an open source software and hardware development environment created on a SoC (System on Chip) type chip system called ESP8266, which contains important elements of the ESP8266 computer. These include CPU (Central Processor Unit), RAM (Random Access Memory), Wi-Fi wireless network, and even a modern operating system and SDK (Software Development Kit). This allows IoT (Internet of Things) to work for all types of projects [10]. Access and use of the ESP8266 as a chip is also complicated. To perform the simplest tasks to turn it on, you need to connect the appropriate analog voltage wires to its pins. It is difficult for amateurs or beginners who want to experiment with it in IoT projects. With this level of integration, the ESP8266 is easier to use as a controller chip built into mass electronics [11].

Designed to conveniently control various remote circuits via a local area network via Wi-Fi or a signal to the Internet [12]. For example, based

on data from the NodeMCU database, it is possible to create a control system by installing light or ventilation controls over the phone, recording sensor readings, and installing many other sensors [13]. The NodeMCU board is more compact, allowing it to be used over more. NodeMCU is "legs" are free to have a breadboard board. The "flash" button on the board is for frames to be transferred to the system, and the "reset" button is for resetting the board [14]. The motherboard of the board ESP8266 occupies a large chip, on which it is possible to install a microprocessor with a frequency of 80 MHz, it can also write to 160 MHz. Additional boards are also available to provide the modules with convenient power. Technical characteristics of the NodeMCU system are shown in Table 2 [15].

Table 2.
Technical characteristics of NodeMCU board.

The size of the board	3x6 sm
Data transmission standards	Wi-Fi 802.11b / g / n
Power supply	5 ~ 12 VDC
Data transfer speed	54, 600 mbit / sec
Distance	100 m
Frequency range	2.4 GGs
Number of devices connected to the network	10
Data transfer type	Wireless, via radio channels
Flash memory capacity	4 Mb
Number of I / O ports	11
Connection type	Micro USB

The NodeMCU board can be powered from a power supply or computer by connecting devices to the controller via a small USB port. The NodeMCU system consumes a small amount of power [16]. NodeMCU Some ports also have additional functions Figure 3.

Figure 3. View of the NodeMCU board.

Using the above DS18B20 temperature sensor and the available capabilities of the NodeMCU board, it is possible to measure the

temperature of the object from different points. Data is transmitted in real time using the NodeMCU board [17]. The DS18B20 temperature sensor on the NodeMCU board connects the data line to the appropriate ports. The DS18B20 temperature sensor communicates using a single-wire protocol, and each sensor has a 64-bit serial code, so the scheme for obtaining temperature from multiple sensors using a single digital PIN is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Structural performance of remote object temperature control from different points.

The ESP8266 is programmed using the Arduino IDE to prepare the Arduino IDE for the DS18B20 temperature sensor and the NodeMCU

board connection scheme to work together using the developed system, so before proceeding, install the ESP8266 system and then record the temperature data from several DS18B20 temperature sensors. [18].

To read the temperature from several sensors, all data lines are connected to the NodeMCU board, as shown in the schematic diagram. In summary, the temperature of the observed object or building can be monitored from multiple points via DS18B20 temperature sensors and NodeMCU systems, and transmitted, received and monitored in real time from the wireless network via the Wi-Fi module, as well as by connecting additional sensors, humidity, pressure and light can also be monitored over time. The developed DS18B20 temperature sensors can be used to conduct real-time experiments in research projects, to monitor the temperature of warehouses or facilities from several points, to organize the transmission of the obtained monitoring results via wireless network through the block diagram of connection to the NodeMCU board.

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